

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF TIME CONTROL IN TREATMENT QUALITY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

This study presents a detailed analysis of the duration of various stages of surgical procedures and the intervals between them, based on the data from computerized patient monitoring in operating rooms and intensive care units. It is demonstrated that average time indicators can serve as an effective tool for assessing patients' condition when developing protocols for similar surgical interventions. It is proposed to use statistical data from patients with a favorable perioperative course and successful treatment outcomes. Integrating such objective time standards obtained using computerized monitoring systems into clinical surgical protocols will significantly increase their practical value when analyzing cases with complications. Furthermore, this approach will improve methods for assessing the quality of medical care and expand prognostic capabilities in identifying the causes of complications by analyzing trends in both individual stages of the procedure and the surgical intervention as a whole.

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Modern diagnostic and treatment technologies require precise adherence to protocol recommendations. The recommended protocols of surgical treatment of cardiovascular diseases do not take into account the time of operations and the preparation of patients for them. The significance of assessing the duration of the surgical and postoperative stages of treatment is not reflected in the protocols known to us [1, 2]. Although in practice, the time of cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB), of aortic cross-clamping, and surgery time are generally always evaluated when analyzing the results of surgical treatment [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. Nevertheless, it must be admitted that systematic research is not being conducted and standards have not been developed.

Known algorithms and assessments of treatment quality do not include the duration of procedures, of treatment stages, intervals between stages, and the operation as a whole. There are no execution time standards even for typical procedures and typical operations. The guidelines for the treatment of acute heart failure of the European Society of Cardiology also do not offer time-based characteristics of procedures and treatment

stages, as well as the organization of protocols by computer means [2]. Although such developments can be traced in scientific research [8, 9]. Moreover, the task of achieving the best quality of treatment permeates the entire process of surgery and perioperative care, including regulating staff-patient interaction over time [4, 5, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. A large number of works are devoted to increasing the productivity of operating rooms, optimizing clinical outcomes, and patient satisfaction [12, 15, 16]. Special attention is paid to the possibilities of monitoring and other information systems in the organization of treatment during and in the space of interaction between specialists providing operations [3, 10, 17, 18].

Research is underway to predict and optimize the total time of surgical interventions for the rational planning of the clinic's treatment process, including methods of mathematical modeling and artificial intelligence [9, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 19, 20], while the duration of the individual stages into which the operational process is actually divided, affecting the overall duration, is little and fragmentary studied [6, 7, 14].

The aim of the study was to compare the duration of the surgical stages and operations in general performed by one surgeon (and different ones) in homogeneous and different operations. The result of the comparison is a fundamental difference between the compared groups and the

division of those for which it is possible to determine standards, as well as an assessment of the information value of the identified operational stages and inter-stage intervals. It is understood that the development of new medical technologies, the improvement of the art of medicine, the emergence of intellectual, informational, technical and technological means, etc. adjusts the estimates of the duration of operational stages, the article focuses on the organization of the clinical and diagnostic process.

Materials and methods. To analyze the effect of the duration of treatment stages on the condition of patients, the results of computer-aided monitoring in operating rooms and the rehabilitation department were used [3, 4, 5]. The case histories of more than 14,000 cardiac surgery patients were analyzed, of which 3,832

computer monitoring protocols were selected for the study, included in the computer database of the automated system for verifying doctor's decisions A.N. Bakoulev Scientific Center for Cardiovascular Surgery for 2008-2022. These patients underwent operations of coronary artery bypass grafting, heart valves replacement, and congenital heart defects repair [18].

The time from the patient's admission to the operating room to the start of cardiopulmonary bypass, the duration of cardiopulmonary bypass, the time after CPB until the patient's transfer to the intensive care unit, and the time of the operation as a whole were recorded. This information is stored in the database (see Fig. 1).

List of patients observed at the DocVue: Brief Information								
	Name	Diagnosis	Operation	T total	T before CPB	T no HR	T after CPD	T CPB
3	Mosk.	Ventric. septal defect	Plastic surgery	3:36	1:36	0:32	1:28	0:56
4	Mish.	Ventric. septal defect	Plastic surgery	4:48	2:06	1:30	1:12	1:36
5	Naza.	TAPVD	Radical correct.	5:36	2:32	0:56	2:08	0:50
6	Naum.	Aortic valve defect	Re-prosthetics	8:24	2:56	1:52	3:36	3:14
7	Niko.	Coronary heart disease	Cor. art. bypass	7:28	3:04	1:28	2:56	1:53
8	Niku.	Mitral valve defect	Valve replacem.	6:08	1:44	2:24	2:00	1:52
9	Pavl.	Ventric. septal defect	Plastic surgery	2:56	1:44	0:24	0:48	0:35
10	Pavu.	Atrial septal defect	Plastic surgery	3:36	1:36	0:24	1:36	0:21
11	Patr.	Mitr. valve defect+IHD	Valve replacem.	7:28	2:32	2:40	2:16	3:28
12	Petr.	Ventric. septal defect	Plastic surgery	4:00	1:36	0:56	1:28	0:56
13	Poji.	Tetralogy of Fallot	Radical correct.	4:24	1:44	1:20	1:04	2:06
14	Popo.	Mitr. +Ao valve defect	Valve replacem.	7:20	2:40	2:32	2:08	1:20
15	Samo.	Partial atrioventr. canal	Radical correct.	4:32	1:52	1:04	1:36	1:24
16	Sido.	Common arterial trunk	Radical correct.	6:16	2:32	2:00	1:44	3:14
17	Sipa.	Ventric. septal defect	Plastic surgery	4:24	1:52	0:56	1:36	1:12
18	Smir.	Patent ductus arterios.	Band., correct.	5:20				
19	Soko.	Aortic valve defect	Valve replacem.	6:32	2:16	0:32	3:44	1:46
20	Soro.	Multiple ASDs	Plastic surgery	6:48	2:16	3:04	1:28	3:44
21	Star.	Atrial septal defect	Plastic surgery	2:08				0:37

Fig. 1. An example of a database of operated cardiac surgery patients. Columns: 1 - last name, first name, patronymic; 2 - fragment of diagnosis; 3 - short name of operation; 4 - total time of operation (hours:minutes); 5-9 time of the operation stages: 5 - T before CPB - the time elapsed from the patient's admission to the operating room to the start of cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB), 6 - T no HR - the time of absence of rhythmic activity of the heart; 7 - T after CPB - the time from the end of CPB to the end of the operation; 8 - the time of CPB according to the protocol of the operation.

In addition to monitoring and measuring time, ECG, pressure in the heart cavities and main vessels, blood oxygen saturation, temperature, etc., as well as, if necessary, cardiac output and pulmonary artery wedge pressure (for severe patients), etc. were monitored [18]. The control errors corresponded to the monitor ones, for example, data was transmitted digitally over a computer network (SDN) without errors [5]. A fragment of the protocol for collecting and storing data for an individual patient in the database is shown in Fig. 2.

The hemodynamic data of each patient were averaged over the stages and procedures of the operation [5, 18]. The average values for each patient were averaged by type of surgical intervention, operating surgeons, and departments. In addition, the data was summarized for the month, quarter, and year. Figure 3 shows the results of such averaging of the data of 18 patients with hypertrophic obstructive cardiomyopathy (HOCMP) at different stages of surgery. The data of each stage were averaged over 10 minutes of observation.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
1	Hemodynamic monitoring protocol													
2														
3	Patient's Name	Surgery Data	№ Oper.	Surgeon	Aneeth.	Early Childhood								
4	M.	14.09	10(1)	Z.	T.	Department								
5														
6														
7	TIME	ABP M	PAP M	T1	T2	T1-T2	HR	NBP S	NBP D	NBP M	RR	ST1	SpO2	PAP S
8	14.09. 7:48			17,8	16,4	1,4	127	125	51	73	25	0,1	98	
9	14.09. 7:57			17,7	16,8	0,9	156	123	84	99	21	-0,1	100	
10	14.09. 8:06			36,5	16,9	19,5	155	124	60	80	28	-0,1	100	
11	14.09. 8:15	17		36,7	33,1	3,5	150				30	-0,2	100	
12	14.09. 8:24	85	4	36,8	34,4	2,3	144	116	53	71	30	-0,1	99	5
13	14.09. 8:33	73	7	36,7	34,9	1,8	138	116	53	71	22	-0,5	100	
14	14.09. 8:42	75	3	36,3	34,9	1,4	148	116	53	71	21	-0,6	100	6
15	14.09. 8:51	59	3	36,1	35,2	1	142	116	53	71	22	-1	100	7
16	14.09. 9:00	72	3	36,2	35,4	0,8	151	116	53	71	24	-1,1	100	6
17	14.09. 9:09	84	6	36,3	35,6	0,7	156	116	53	71	29	-0,2	100	9
18	14.09. 9:18	47	4	36,1	35,6	0,4	160	103	36	56	24	-0,1	100	7
19	14.09. 9:27	31	3	32,7	35	-2,3	0	103	36	56	10			
20	14.09. 9:36	34	3	31,8	33,7	-1,8	0	103	36	56	3		97	
21	14.09. 9:45	46	2	34,3	33,5	0,8	116	103	36	56	20	-1,1	99	5
22	14.09. 9:54	73	3	36,1	34,2	1,9	185	103	36	56	21	-0,9	100	6
23	14.09. 10:03	65	5	36	35	1	161	103	36	56	27	-0,4	100	9
24	14.09. 10:12	76	5	36	35,5	0,5	152	103	36	56	27	-0,1	100	9
25	14.09. 10:21	71	6	36	35,6	0,4	146	105	37	58	25	0	100	9
26	14.09. 10:30	80	5	36	35,6	0,4	148	105	37	58	27	-0,1	100	7
27	14.09. 10:39	85	5	36	35,6	0,4	146	105	37	58	28	-0,3	100	8
28	14.09. 10:48	77	4	36,1	35,7	0,4	155	105	37	58	30	-0,6	100	7
29	14.09. 10:57	74		36	35,7	0,3	147	105	37	58	25	-0,7	100	
30	14.09. 11:06	75		36	35,7	0,3	151	105	37	58	25	-0,9	100	
31	14.09. 11:15	71		36,2	35,8	0,5	154	129	92	107	30	-1,1	100	
32	14.09. 11:24	83		36,4	35,8	0,6	151	129	92	107	27	-1,1	100	
33	14.09. 11:33	73		36,6	35,9	0,7	96	129	92	107		-1,3	100	
34	14.09. 11:42	71		36,8	36	0,7	152	129	92	107	28	-1,2	100	
35	14.09. 11:51	66		36,9	36,2	0,7	155	129	92	107	29	-1,3	100	
36	14.09. 12:00							129	92	107				
37	14.09. 12:09							129	92	107				
38	14.09. 12:18													

Fig. 2. An example of a protocol for monitoring hemodynamics during surgery, saved in MS Excel. Time is the date and time of measurement (day, month, hours, minutes), ABP M is the average blood pressure, PAP M is the average pressure in the pulmonary artery, T1, T2, T1-T2, respectively, rectal, skin temperatures and their gradient, HR is the heart rate; noninvasive blood pressure: systolic - NBP S, diastolic - NBP D, mean - NBP M; RR – respiratory rate, ST1 – ST segment, SpO2 – pulse oximetry, systolic pulmonary blood pressure - PAP S.

Fig. 3. Trends in the average hemodynamic parameters of patients with hypertrophic obstructive cardiomyopathy: blood pressure – systolic (ABP S), diastolic (ABP D), mean (ABP M), heart rate (HR).

As an example, Table 1 shows a fragment of a statistical analysis of monitoring data in operating rooms for one month.

Table 1.

An example of a statistical generalization for a month of observation of hemodynamic data in the congenital heart defects repair in children from one to two years old

Stages	HR	SpO2	ABP S	ABP D	ABP M	Pulse
Before CPB	107,5±3,3	95,0±0,9	103,7±2,4	56,8±1,1	71,3±1,3	100,8±3,8
Cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB)		92,3±0,9	57,8±1,5	45,9±1,5	50,1±1,4	
After CPB	115,2±2,8	97,5±0,5	101,1±2,0	55,7±1,0	70,6±1,2	113,8±2,3

Fig. 4. Screenshot. Trends of each heart rate cycle when changing pacing modes. Labels: 1 – left ventricular pacing, 2 – no pacing, 3 – right ventricular pacing.

Figure 4 shows the curves of cyclic control (blood pressure: systolic ABP S, diastolic ABP D, and mean ABP M and T=1/HR) of patient C. with aortic valve replacement in the postoperative period during a change of cardiac stimulation modes. 18 minutes of observation: from 13:41 to 13:46, the left ventricle was stimulated, and from 13:46 to 13:52, the right ventricle was stimulated. Changes in mean arterial pressure were mainly determined by changes in diastolic pressure up to 25%, while systolic pressure changed little up to 10%.

A fragment of this patient's data during the shutdown of left ventricular stimulation (13.41.22.66) and the transition to his own rhythm is presented in table 2.

Each line contains data on one heart rate cycle. Such cycle-by-cycle monitoring (of each heartbeat cycle) makes it possible to accurately determine the time of transition from one stimulation mode to another and its correlation with hemodynamic parameters [18].

Results of statistical processing of the surgical stages duration. Let us consider the processed data of patients during cardiac surgeries to treat congenital heart defects (atrial septal defect and interventricular septal defect, correction of Ebstein’s anomaly, correction of double trunk defect, patent ductus arteriosus, etc.), acquired heart defects (aortic valve replacement, mitral valve replacement), coronary artery bypass grafting, etc. over the course of a year (Table 2). The processing was carried out for each stage for each patient individually and for all groups of patients (a detailed description is given in the publications [4, 5]).

Table 2.

Months	Number of patients	Time from the beginning of monitoring to CPB		Time of absence of rhythmic cardiac activity		Time from the start of the heart to the end of the operation		Total duration of the operation	
		M	Σ	M	σ	M	σ	M	σ
January	122	2:11	0:33	1:15	0:41	1:59	0:44	5:25	1:30
February	104	2:11	0:49	1:08	0:39	2:06	0:44	5:25	1:38
March	108	2:06	0:38	1:08	0:34	1:58	1:00	4:50	1:51
April	151	2:03	0:40	1:01	0:38	1:59	0:56	5:03	1:38
May	189	1:36	0:38	1:10	0:35	1:30	0:38	4:23	1:32
June	155	2:16	0:50	1:13	0:43	2:02	1:16	4:53	2:06
July	109	1:55	0:42	1:07	0:52	1:55	0:52	4:39	1:52
August	126	2:17	0:42	1:11	0:48	1:54	1:00	4:42	1:56
September	153	2:00	0:32	1:04	0:36	1:48	0:51	4:31	1:38
October	185	2:12	0:34	1:10	0:42	2:07	1:07	5:03	1:56
November	97	1:39	0:44	0:59	0:34	1:53	1:12	4:48	1:52
December	146	2:07	0:37	1:09	0:37	1:58	0:53	4:39	1:43
Mean M		2:03	0:40	1:08	0:40	1:56	0:56	4:52	1:46
% standard deviation from the mean σ %		33%		59%		49%		36%	
Error of the mean m		0:03	0:01	0:01	0:01	0:02	0:03	0:05	0:03

Table 2 presents statistical estimates of the duration of the main stages of cardiac surgery with detailed computer monitoring: means (M), standard deviations (σ), errors of the means (m). The following stages are

highlighted: before the main stage of the operation (before cardiopulmonary bypass start), the duration was 2:03±00:03 with σ=40 minutes, i.e. the average variation was 33%. The duration of the main stage –cardiopulmonary bypass itself – was 1:08±00:01 (Table 2)

with an average variation of 60% ($\sigma=40$ minutes). The duration of the stage after the end of cardiopulmonary bypass until the end of the operation is comparable with the stage before it and was $1:56\pm 00:02$ with an average variation of 48% ($\sigma=56$ minutes). The average variance in the total duration of operations was 37%, and the total duration of cardiac surgery was $04:52\pm 00:05$, which is comparable to international experience. For example, in the study by Costa et al. [6], the duration of cardiac surgery was $06:23\pm 13$ with a variance of 49%.

It was found out that the duration of surgeries in operating rooms with computerized monitoring ranged from 2 hours 32 minutes to 10 hours 56 minutes. The

period before the start of cardiopulmonary bypass lasted from 32 minutes to 4 hours 48 minutes. The duration of cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB) varied from 16 minutes to 3 hours 12 minutes. The minimum period after CPB until the end of the surgery was 40 minutes, and the longest period was up to 4 hours 56 minutes.

Let us consider, as an example, a detailed analysis of one of the periods of surgical intervention – the time from the start of invasive hemodynamic monitoring to the start of cardiopulmonary bypass, selecting patients for whom this stage lasted more than 2 hours 30 minutes (Table 3; data are given for a month of observation).

Table 3.

An example of the duration of the surgical stages of patients in whom the stage before CPB exceeded 2 hours 30 minutes during a month of observation (hours:minutes)

Stages	Difference in time between the scheduled start of surgery and the actual start	Difference in time from the start of monitoring to the placement of an arterial catheter	Time before CPB	Time of absence of cardiac rhythmic activity	Time after CPB	Total time of surgery	Time from the end of monitoring of one patient to the start of monitoring of the next one
Mean	0:48	0:32	2:55	1:23	2:21	6:41	1:12
Error of the mean	0:52	0:45	0:29	0:41	1:01	1:32	0:45
Maximum	2:39	2:07	4:12	2:51	4:39	10:12	2:15
Minimum	0:09	0:00	2:33	0:45	1:03	4:12	0:45

There were 35 such patients. A period of more than 4 hours was observed in two patients undergoing repeat surgery for total repair of tetralogy of Fallot and total repair of double outlet right ventricle. A period of more than 3 hours was observed in 12 patients, 16% of whom were repeat patients, 40% of whom underwent combined procedures with multivalve replacement and coronary artery bypass grafting and mammary coronary artery bypass grafting. It should be noted that for the stage under consideration before cardiopulmonary bypass, the range of means was small – 16%. For the remaining stages, the range in these patients was more than 40%, and for the first two stages (Table 3, columns 2 and 3), it exceeded the means themselves – 108% and 140%.

Similar operations performed by one surgeon.

Let us consider the data on aortic valve replacement surgeries performed by surgeon A.¹ during a quarter (see Table 4). The average variation in the duration of

the stages of the operations and the operations as a whole is small and ranged from 4 to 14%. On average, both the stages before and after cardiopulmonary bypass lasted approximately two hours: $02:08\pm 00:05$ and $02:18\pm 00:12$, respectively. The time of absence of heart rhythmic activity (the main stage – cardiopulmonary bypass lasted on average $01:06\pm 00:04$). The total duration of the operation was comparable with the data for the year (see Table 2) and amounted to $05:30\pm 16$.

As can be seen from Table 4 (rows "Maximum" and "Minimum"), there were significant differences in the duration of stages and the overall operation. Thus, the duration of the operation ranged from 4 hours to 9 hours 27 minutes. Deviations from the average for shorter operations require study to identify time-saving potential, while for longer operations, an analysis of the causes of complications and the overall organization of the surgical process is needed [4].

¹ The surgeons' surnames are given arbitrarily in the alphabetical order and have no relation to the abbreviation of the real surname.

Table 4.

Database printout. Example of the duration of interoperative intervals and stages of aortic valve replacement surgery performed by surgeon A.

Full name patient	Duration of stages						
	Time between the scheduled start of the operation and the actual start	Time from the start of noninvasive monitoring to the placement of an arterial catheter	Time from the start of monitoring to CPB	Time of absence of cardiac rhythmic activity	Time from cardiac start to the end of the operation	Time from the end of monitoring of one patient to the start of monitoring of the next	Duration of the operation
L.	0:30	0:16	1:52	1:12	3:20	1:12	6:24
M.	0:14	0:24	2:24	1:28	2:24	1:36	6:16
A.	0:30	0:24	1:44	0:48	1:36	1:12	4:08
D.	0:38	0:48	2:08	0:40	1:28	2:16	4:16
H.	0:22	0:32	2:24	0:40	2:08		5:12
K.	0:06	0:24	2:00	1:04	1:20	0:56	4:24
C.	0:04	0:24	1:36	0:32	1:52		4:00
K.	0:44	0:24	2:00	2:00	2:00	5:12	5:12
F.	0:30	0:16	2:40	1:28	2:32	6:40	6:40
I.	0:38	0:08	1:44	1:28	2:24	5:36	5:36
C.	0:54	0:12	2:00	0:48	2:24		5:12
Sh.	2:00	0:12	2:12	1:12	2:00		5:24
D.	1:06		1:48	1:00	2:00	4:48	4:48
J.	0:54		1:48	1:12	1:48	4:48	4:48
N.	0:18	0:27	3:09	1:12	3:00		7:21
Ch.	0:18	0:18	2:42	1:03	5:42		9:27
K.	0:36	0:09	2:06	0:54	1:48		4:48
T.	0:42	0:00	1:48	1:39	2:24		5:51
G.	0:36	0:45	2:33	0:45	1:39	4:57	4:57
Mean	0:36	0:19	2:08	1:06	2:18	3:33	5:30
Error of the mean	0:05	0:02	0:05	0:04	0:12	0:27	0:16
Maximum	2:00	0:48	3:09	2:00	5:42	6:40	9:27
Minimum	0:04	0:05	1:36	0:32	1:20	0:56	4:00

The unfilled cells are due to the fact that it was not possible to reliably estimate the time of this stage.

These are the results of a single surgeon. The obtained data of the stages duration can be used as reference data when planning such surgeries, provided that the surgical risks are low (the surgical period is assumed to be uncomplicated and the outcome is a cure for the patient) [4, 5].

To confirm this conclusion, data obtained from atrial septal defect repair procedures performed by different surgeons were reviewed. The average duration of 16 procedures performed by surgeon B. was 3:47±0:10, with an individual range from 2:26 to 5:24. For surgeon C., the average duration of the stages of 24 similar procedures was 3:42±0:22, close to those of surgeon B.

It was found out that for similar operations performed by one surgeon, the mean time error is:

- the maximum range of duration from the start of non-invasive monitoring to the placement of an arterial catheter ranged from 7 to 19%,

- from the start of invasive monitoring to CPB from 3 to 7%,

- absence of cardiac rhythmic activity from 4 to 18%,

- from cardiac activation to the end of surgery from 9 to 17%,

- the duration of surgery as a whole from 4 to 13% [4, 5].

Comparing these data with the data obtained from similar operations performed by different surgeons, it was determined that in these cases the range was higher.

Similar and different operations performed by the same surgeon. Let us compare the duration of operations performed in the same department by two surgeons, G. and D., when they were first assistants and when they performed the operations independently (Tables 5a and 5b). Tables 5a and 5b show that the difference in time between the scheduled start of the opera-

tion and the start of the patient's monitoring was significantly smaller when they operated as first assistants (by 57% and 58%, Table 5a and 57% and 44%, Table 6b). Surgeon G. spent less time installing an arterial catheter when he operated as first assistant (by 17% and 8%), while surgeon D. spent more time in a similar situation (by 9% and 22%). As this result was observed both in the case of similar surgeries (ventricular septal defect repair, Table 5a) and in different surgeries (Table 5b), then it most likely characterizes the personal characteristics of the surgeons. Two more interesting

points should be noted in these tables. The time of CPB in similar surgeries (ventricular septal defect repair, Table 5a) was practically the same as the annual average (Table 2), lasting on average approximately one hour, and did not depend on the operating team, in which surgeons G. and D. acted as operating surgeons or assistants.

At other stages before and after CPB, the time expenditure of surgeons G. and D., if they acted as assistants, increased to 20% for similar operations (Table 5a) and up to 40% for different ones.

Table 5a.

Duration of stages and interstage intervals in patients with ventricular septal defect repair surgery (hours: minutes).

Operating surgeon	Number of patients	Number of patients with complications/% of total number of patients	Difference in time between the scheduled start of surgery and the actual start	Difference in time from the start of monitoring to the placement of an arterial catheter	Time from the start of monitoring to CPB	Absence of cardiac rhythmic activity	Time from cardiac start to the end of surgery	Time from the end of monitoring of one patient to the start of monitoring of the next	Total duration of surgery
Surgeon G. - assistant	4	-	00:33 ±00:06	00:24 ±00:18	02:28 ±00:08	01:01 ±00:11	01:49 ±00:11	01:05 ±00:01	05:19 ±00:13
Surgeon G. - lead surgeon	6	-	01:19 ±00:24	00:29 ±00:05	01:5 3±00:03	01:05 ±00:08	01:21 ±00:14	01:12 ±00:00	04:20 ± 00:18
Difference in %*			-58	-17	23	-6	26	18	-10
Surgeon D. - assistant	10	-	00:33 ±00:04	00:32 ±00:04	02:2 0±00:07	01:11 ±00:04	01:49 ±00:08	01:18 ±00:20	05:12 ±00:11
Surgeon D. - lead surgeon	10	2/20%	01:10 ±00:13	00:29 ±00:02	01:46 ±00:06	01:08 ±00:03	01:07 ±00:06	01:56 ±00:34	04:0 3±00:09
Difference in %**			-52	9	24	4	38	22	-26

The difference in %* shows how much more or less (-) time Surgeon G. spends on the surgical steps as the first assistant compared to performing them independently.

The difference in %** shows how much more or less (-) time Surgeon D. spends on the surgical steps as the first assistant compared to performing them independently.

Table 5b.

Duration (hours: minutes) of surgical stages and inter-stage intervals in children of the first year of life, operated on in one department

Operating surgeon	Number of patients	Number of patients with complications/% of total number of patients	Difference in time between the scheduled start of surgery and the actual start	Difference in time from the start of monitoring to the placement of an arterial catheter	Time from the start of monitoring to CPB	Absence of cardiac rhythmic activity	Time from cardiac start to the end of surgery	Time from the end of monitoring of one patient to the start of monitoring of the next	Total duration of surgery
Surgeon G. - assistant	51	7/14%	00:27 ±00:12	00:31 ±00:10	02:23 ±00:19	01:38 ±00:20	01:43 ±00:28	01:47 ±00:44	05:51 ±00:48
Surgeon G. - lead surgeon	36	2/4%	01:04 ±00:10	00:3 4±00:04	01:45 ±00:05	00:51 ±00:03	01:16 ±00:06	01:47 ±00:08	03:35 ±00:10
Difference in %*			-57	-8	27	42	13	47	0
Surgeon D. - assistant	35	3/9%	00:33 ±00:09	00:36 ±00:05	02:22 ±00:14	01:11 ±00:05	01:48 ±00:10	01:53 ±00:28	05:33 ±00:20
Surgeon D. - lead surgeon	22	3/14%	00:59 ±00:14	00:28 ±00:02	01:45 ±00:07	00:57 ±00:04	01:14 ±00:06	02:12 ±00:28	03:51 ±00:14
Difference in %**			-44	22	27	20	31	40	-14

References * and ** correspond to Table 5a.

Characteristics of the time between surgical stages.

Summarizing the data for a year of observation showed that the duration of the stage from the time when the patient was admitted to the operating room according to the schedule until connection to monitoring (before the installation of ECG electrodes, an SpO₂ sensor, and a blood pressure cuff) was quite long: the indicators deviate from the mean value by an average of 92% (mean duration 50±3 minutes). For similar procedures performed by the same surgeon, for example, during aortic valve replacement, this time averaged 36±5 minutes (Table 4). The range of time for aortic valve replacement surgeries ranged from 4 minutes to 2 hours, and for atrial septal defect repair, from 4 minutes to 1 hour 38 minutes. These data demonstrate significant potential for shortening of this stage. The importance of determining the onset of surgery has also been emphasized by other researchers. For example, Vladu et al. [9] are developing special computational algorithms to control the start time of surgery to improve the efficiency of operating room use.

The duration of the surgical phase from the start of noninvasive monitoring to arterial catheter placement averages 27±1 minutes (maximum 4 hours 21 minutes, minimum 12 minutes). This phase characterizes the time elapsed from the moment monitoring is established to the moment

the arterial catheter is inserted—the start of invasive blood pressure measurement, which is the actual start of the surgical procedure—the invasive intervention. It is necessary to investigate the causes of prolonged expectation time for patients already admitted to the operating room before procedures begin, so that measures can be taken to streamline this process.

These studies echo the work of Costa et al. [6], who examined the time spent in the operating room and the time of the surgical procedure itself. They identified patterns in the duration of surgical stages which may aid in operating room planning and reduce delays.

The intervals between the end of monitoring for one patient and the start of monitoring for the next one, i.e., the interval between surgeries, on average 1 hour 12 minutes (±3 minutes). The individual range, from 12 minutes to 5 hours 4 minutes, indicates the need for the analysis of potential time reserves. It should be noted that computerized monitoring allows for an accurate assessment of all stages and interstage intervals, as opposed to expert assessment of time elapsed [21].

An example of similar surgeries. Let's consider the data of two patients with aortic defects, operated on by the same surgeon (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Duration of the surgical stages of aortic valve replacement in patients Ch. and S.

Patient Ch., 52 years old, with calcified aortic valve disease (stenosis and insufficiency grade 2), with paroxysmal atrial fibrillation, underwent aortic valve

replacement surgery with a mechanical prosthesis AST No. 25 under CPB, hypothermia and pharmaco-cold cardioplegia (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Hemodynamic trends during aortic valve replacement surgery in patient Ch.: systolic (ABP S), diastolic (ABP D) and mean (ABP M) blood pressure.

Fig. 6. Hemodynamic trends during aortic valve replacement surgery in patient S.: systolic (ABP S), diastolic (ABP D) and mean (ABP M) blood pressure.

Patient S., 52 years old, with aortic valve insufficiency, underwent a similar operation of aortic valve replacement with a mechanical prosthesis AST No. 23 (Fig. 6).

In Fig. 4, the last columns show the duration of the surgical intervention for patient Ch. (duration of the operation 09:27) and S. (04:00). The difference in the duration of the operation was determined by the fact that the stages before cardiopulmonary bypass and cardiopulmonary bypass stage in patient Ch. were longer by 01:06 and 04:10, respectively. The longer period of cardiopulmonary bypass was due to an episode of rhythm disturbance - atrial tachyarrhythmia with a drop in hemodynamic parameters - occurring during the hemostasis stage. Due to this, cardiopulmonary bypass was restarted. During an attempt to end CPB, multiple episodes of rhythm disturbance with a drop in hemodynamic parameters occurred. The rhythm was restored with defibrillation and medication. As a result, in the early postoperative period, patient Ch. required greater cardiotoxic support: adrenaline at a dose of 0.085 mcg/kg/min and dopamine at a dose of 5 mcg/kg/min, in contrast to patient S., who received a minimal dose of dobutamine (3.65 mcg/kg/min) in the early postoperative period.

Hemodynamic analysis. The duration of the surgical period significantly affects the postoperative patient's condition [5, 8]. Data processing showed that the patient's hemodynamics is affected by the duration of the following stages: cardiopulmonary bypass, before cardiopulmonary bypass, especially the part from admission to the operating room until intubation and after the main stage of the operation until its completion [4, 5]. As an example, we present the monitoring data of patients P. (operative duration 03:36) and B. (operative duration 05:36), who ventricular septal defect repair under cardiopulmonary bypass and pharmacologic cardioplegia (Table 6). Rows 2-4 present the monitoring data for patient P., and rows 5-7 for patient B. For patient B., the time before the start of cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB) was 01:12, the CPB time was 00:26, and the post CPB time was 00:32 longer than for patient P. This affected his hemodynamics by a decrease in his arterial pressure: ABP S, ABP D and ABP M by almost half, and SpO2 by 15% during cardiopulmonary bypass, an increase in heart rate by 15%, and an increase in pulmonary artery pressure (PAP S) by 43%, PAP M by 85%, and PAP D by three times after the main stage of the operation (see Table 6).

Table 6.

A fragment of statistical analysis of monitoring data for patients with short and long surgical periods

Patients	Stage	HR	SpO2	ABP S	ABP D	ABP M	PAP S	PAP D	PAP M
P.	Before CPB	115,4±4,3	99,8±0,2	109,2±4,4	59,4±2,9	77,9±3,4	6,8±0,2	2,5±0,3	4,3±0,3
	CPB		96,6±2,2	72,8±3,4	51,2±1,9	63,2±2,6	7,0±1,0	3,1±0,6	4,9±0,6
	After CPB	122,7±1,8	100,0±0,0	117,0±2,4	65,1±1,4	87,1±1,7	9,0±0,2	5,6±0,2	7,2±0,2
B.	Before CPB	127,4±2,8	99,2±0,2	96,2±1,3	56,4±1,2	69,9±1,6	6,8±0,7	2,2±0,5	3,9±0,4
	CPB		84,6±2,2	44,1±4,9	31,4±0,9	35,9±1,4			4,0±1,5
	After CPB	146,1±1,5	99,0±0,1	99,9±1,4	57,3±1,3	69,9±1,5	9,7±2,1	8,6±0,5	7,2±0,2

Statistical verification of the last result was impossible, since the patients' condition significantly depends on the administered potent drugs. The administration of potent drugs is not monitored, and at the same time, their type and doses vary greatly from patient to patient and even during treatment of the same patient. This circumstance excludes the feasibility of statistical analysis for large samples and makes the results of an individual approach more effective [3, 5, 10, 18, 22]. Long-term observations have convinced us that an increase in the duration of operations increases the risk of complications, especially if the treatment is accompanied by high doses of cardiotonics in combination with other complications [5].

Therefore, it is advisable to monitor and use objective computer-based monitoring of patient condition parameters to provide treatment, as these parameters also determine the timing of surgical treatment stages. For this purpose, it is necessary to develop and include appropriate standards in protocols and, even more importantly, to present trends in patient condition parameters (clinical, hemodynamic, and biochemical) as they depend on time, as well as the course of the surgery itself, also over time, when analyzing complications [3, 5, 10, 18, 22].

To summarize, we hope that in the near future, operating room information systems will precisely control all surgical conditions: the parameters of the surgical equipment, the premises, the actions and physical condition of the medical team and, of course, the objective condition of the patient [9, 16, 18, 23]. With cycle-by-cycle analysis, it is possible to control thousands and hundreds of thousands of measurements and calculations in real time, therefore the dispersion and analysis of some stages of operations required long-term precision statistical and clinical-physiological data analysis [10, 18, 22].

Thus, A.N. Bakoulev Scientific Center for Cardiovascular Surgery implemented planned, ongoing computer-based monitoring and analysis of the duration of surgical stages, including average values, variance, and determination of dependencies on the severity of the initial condition, type of anesthesia, etc. As a result, we obtained reference values for the duration of surgical stages for orientation and inclusion in treatment protocols.

Conclusions. The average duration of the identified surgical stages is compact and stable, consistent with the patient's condition and the best international practices.

The individual variation in surgical duration and surgical stages varies greatly from patient to patient compared to the average values. Therefore, for complex cases, detailed personalized monitoring of the stages, taking into account hemodynamic status, is necessary [3, 5, 10].

It should be noted that the variability in the duration of the stages of the surgical process, assessed using computer monitoring, indicates that:

- the quality of diagnostic preparation for surgery and an insufficiently accurate diagnosis lead to additional time expenditure and changes to the preliminary treatment plan;

- an increase in the time from the patient's arrival in the operating room to the start of the surgical process (induction of anesthesia) leads to a deterioration in the patient's condition.

Treatment protocols for cardiovascular diseases, both surgical and medical, should take into account the time required for treatment stages and procedures. This will improve quality assessments and prognostic capabilities for both individual stages and for procedures as a whole, compared to currently used methods [22].

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